

The Incredible World of Blockchains

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INTRODUCTION:

An overview of what blockchains are, the functionality behind them and ultimately the applications of it: Digital Identity, Cloud Storage, Smart contracts, Trading and ultimately a value-based economy.

AIM:

To convey the urgency and importance of Block Chain and how it can alter our world in a variety of ways. It is also to inform the audience on the extreme utility of block chains, and that the applicability of the idea is nearly universal. Block chain aims to de-centralize, disrupt and replace many existing areas from cyber-security to the voting system.

KEYWORDS:

Block chain; hash; encoded

BIOGRAPHY:

Siddarth is 14 years old studying at University of Toronto Schools. He is the C.E.O of Snype, a bio-medical company with a lot on its agenda. He has worked on many projects in subjects like recurrent neural networks, neuroscience and more.